

Good participatory practice for COVID-19 research: the case of a COVID-19 prevention study

Supplementary material: Questions and statements by theme and session

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Session codes: **MORU**= The Mahidol-Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU), Bangkok, Thailand; **FTM**= Mahidol University, Faculty of Tropical Medicine (FTM), Bangkok, Thailand; **HREIG**=MORU Health Research and Interest Group (HREIG), Bangkok (conducted online); **CR1**=Chiangrai Clinical Research Unit (CCRU), Chiangrai, Thailand; **OUH**=The Horton Hospital, Oxford University Hospitals (OUH) NHS Foundation Trust, Banbury, United Kingdom; **LAO**=Mahosot Hospital, Vientiane, Laos; **HCM**=Hospital for Tropical Diseases, Ho Ci Minh City, Vietnam; **NPL**=13 B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal

Question number: **1**=Reasons for wanting or not to participate in study; **2**= Information that would strengthen or change your decision; **3**=Open ended question

Session	Statement/question	question nr	Theme 1	Theme 2
CR1	Wants to join but I worry that I will be given a placebo which makes it unprofitable from taking medication	3	safety and risk benefit	
CR1	I worry about an increased risk of getting covid infections because they might have to join a large group of people.	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR1	Because sign and symptoms of covid of people who get covid infection, there's no sign or minimum sign & symptoms, we don't know they've already got infection but they come to us, should we wear PPE all the time? For prevention, assume they get.	3	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR2	I'm still young, risk and benefits are not worth. Low mortality rate of Covid-19	1	safety and risk benefit	safety and risk benefit and risk benefit

CR2	I'm not in contact with patients	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Because I'm not sure I will ever get COVID-19 infection	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	May benefit from prophylaxis	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Will medicine affect on our body?	2	safety and risk benefit	
FTM	Concern about drug interactions with current medications.	2	safety and risk benefit	
FTM	Concern about drug effects to comorbidities	2	safety and risk benefit	
LAO	Want to protect my self	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Why I know if I do not contact the covid-19 patient	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	If I have hypertension, can I participate to the study? (I take Prednolol/atenolol every day)	2	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Not able to buy chloroquine here: 50% better than 0%	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	protect myself	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	It might work so I might benefit and so might society	1	social value and st. rationale	

MORU	Increase chance to prevent myself from COVID-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I may be protected	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	it might protect me	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I don't want to die yet	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Very sensitive to drugs	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	it would put my family members at risk	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	planning to have a child	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Don't like needles (blood collection)	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	I live with the old, immune compromised people	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I don't want to take the risk	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	I have my mom and dad at home, not sure if this study is safe for them	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	It might work so I might benefit and so might society	1	social value and st. rationale	

OUH1	if more attention from medics	2	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	No because of needle phobia	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Not keen to participate, don't take medication unless strictly necessary	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Allergic to CQ	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	No because I am awaiting to start IVF treatment	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	No because I'm worried about breast feeding	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR1	In case that a participant in the project has symptoms similar to COVID-19, will this affect the participation or not?	3	design and commitments	
CR1	If It would be possible if consent form mentions side effect of chloroquine and concomitant medication.	2	design and commitments	
CR1	if the initial step that is participating in the project, The participants are still in good health. But if we have participated in the project and during that time, we have symptoms of flu or illness for otherer causes that are similar to COVID-19, and we	2	design and commitments	
CR1	I want to join, but because there are many procedures to do, such as checking the fever every day, reporting symptoms every day and must take medicine every day. Therefore may not have time to participate.	2	design and commitments	
CR1	Factors that made the decision not to participate in the project are the drugs used in the study, including chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine. And has one drug that is used as a placebo If the participant is informed, it may be the reason to decide not t	2	design and commitments	
CR1	3 months for taking chloroquine is too long. Can it reduce taking time?	2	design and commitments	

CR1	I think there will be in the consent form, they will inform the participant first. I have one more question I think if a nurse in ward they have many work to do. If I forgot to take medicine, maybe one time, are you ok?	1	design and commitments	
CR1	As you know, medicine has a side effect for liver. I wonder, the study team will check the liver function test, BUN, Creatinine or not?	2	design and commitments	
CR1	I have one question, if someone has side effect, cannot take medicine, and cannot tolerate with it, can't take it anymore until complete 3 months, can they stop taking medicine?	2	design and commitments	
CR1	If we can't tolerate with medicine but we want continue participate in study. Can we do?	3	design and commitments	design and commitments
CR1	I have a question, suppose, nowadays people have allergy, have a cold a lot, it's similar to Covid, right? Suppose, in the beginning we're joining study, we don't have that symptom but once we take that medicine for a while then we have allergy or cold and we have to take otherers medicine, too. What will be happen? Will it be ok?	3	design and commitments	
CR1	Will there be specify which medicine that have interact with CQ in the consent form?	3	design and commitments	
CR1	Yes, if participant in this study, we take CQ but after that we have to get this medicine, so?	3	design and commitments	
CR1	Suppose, we have to take, it means we have to out of the study, right? In case they have some disease that necessary to take those medicine. Do they have to withdraw? While they are in the study.	3	design and commitments	
CR1	If the nurse or any participants they join the study and one day they have sign or symptoms that suspected they get covid-19 infection, how do they do because they are not the patient in the hospital, right? And the doctor, she worry that the doctor who t	3	design and commitments	
CR1	At least it's not the fake one, the placebo anotherer one might be anotherer medicine which is in the same group or same qualification/attribute/affect or whatnot. To be the compare, better than we take but nothering.	2	design and commitments	

CR1	The information would change our mind, this project participants have to take medicine for 3 months and during this period, while they're participate in the project and then we found that our participant or people in the society get Covid-19 infection quite a lot. So, can we assume it doesn't work or should they continue taking medicine until the end of the project or should they stop because they don't know which medicine they take?	2	design and commitments	
CR1	Suppose, if Covid stop within 2 months, should we continue taking medicine, continue study?	3	design and commitments	
CR1	Does chloroquine have liver-toxicity? can we do liver function tests for participants?	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR1	The reason for change the decision is that when you join as a volunteer and taking medication, there are still otherer volunteers who have a high number of Covid-19 infections, which may make predictions that the drug cannot be prevented. And anotherer reason is that after taking the drug, there are symptoms or severe side effects, cannot tolerate to eat for up to 3 months	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR1	For me, I want to join this study but if I know side effect of the medicine. I think the consent form have the information?	1	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR1	What I worry, what would affect on my decision is coming to join, there will be a group of people come, it might be follow up, make appointment to see researcher team. It probably increase risk to contact with a lot of people or not? Don't know researcher researcher team has Covid? Because researcher team close and contact with many people.	3	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR1	Due to Covid-19's disease. There is no best treatment or Guideline for care. If participating in a research project, it will be useful to find methods. And participation will not affect much of daily life, and otherer methods of prevention must still be done.	2	social value and st. rationale	design and commitments

CR1	I think I would join because it's the beneficial project, because we don't know clearly how to treat and how to prevent. If this study is alternative choice. I think I will join in order to have more choice but what I'm worry is as the nurse has to work morning shift, afternoon, and night shift. I may not have time because we have to take medicine, measure temperature twice a day, take medicine every day. I afraid that I probably forget and have to report symptoms via mobile app every day. Some nurse might not expert about mobile app, it might make someone worry about how to use mobile app, how to send, how to do. Anotherer thing I concern is, if CQ is alternative for protection Covid but if I, myself have to random and receive placebo, someone might be worry what we take every day is nothering, not benefit. And we don't know what we'll receive, real medicine or placebo.	3	social value and st. rationale	design and commitments
CR1	In the study, we have to take medicine for 3 months, it's quite long. Do you have any reason why they need to take for 3 months? Can it less than that?	3	social value and st. rationale	
CR1	I have a question, Is there anybody here [research unit team] will participate?	1		
CR2	Do you think, we will pay more for F/U lab after we start CQ or spend for treatment side effect of CQ?	1	design and commitments	
CR2	There could be many confounding factors, between control and placebo	2	design and commitments	
CR2	Healing measurement from side effect of Chloroquine	2	design and commitments	
CR2	Monitoring side effect closely, has clear guideline if there are adverse effect on participants.	2	design and commitments	
CR2	Clarify on screening or prevent side effect from the drug	2	design and commitments	
CR2	I would like to know	2	other	
CR2	I'm not sure, not enough information	2	other	
CR2	Because afraid of complication	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Risk more than benefit, side effects of medicine, unclear indication.	1	safety and risk benefit	safety and risk benefit

CR2	Because Chloroquine may have side effect	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	First, Chloroquine has too many side effects. Second, I think I won't get Covid-19 infection even though I work in the hospital, the best prevention is PPE, Mask, hand washing, those are better protected	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Because Chloroquine has side effects more than potential/expected benefits	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Because worry about side effect of medicine	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Too risk for cornea	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Because of side effect of Chloroquine	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Current knowledge, it's unclear benefits if compare with side effects	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Chloroquine has a lot side effects. It won't help if taking medication but not protect ourselves (No washing hands/wear mask)	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Worry about potential side effects	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Taking CQ has more risks than benefits	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	CQ has side effects quite a lot when compared to risks and benefits	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	because side effects of medicine are quite a lot, every physician are not contact Covid-19 patients every case	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Afraid and worry about the side effects of medicine	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Worry about the side effects of medicine and I think the chance of getting infection is low if we have good self prevention	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale

CR2	Because medicine has side effects quite a lot	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	I think I'm sure I can wear preventive equipment	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	A lot of side effects of medicine	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Would benefit in a high risk area with lots of covid patients	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Worry about CQ side effects especially macular degeneration	1	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Don't want to participate because side effect of medicine, we can protect ourselves by wash our hands, wearing face shield, there's no paper support Chloroquine can be really prevented.	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Have reference support about efficacy and side effect	2	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Providing information about side effect of medicine clearly, how to heal, manage when SE happen (Reversible, Irreversible)	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR2	There is the information confirming that what side effect to those who has been taking medicine for a while, how many percent, how many staff who has been taking medicine for prophylaxis are still get Covid-19 infection	2	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Risk of taking Chloroquine e.g. serious side effects	2	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	Side effect and benefits of medicine	2	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Side effect of medicine. Literature review, previous study if there're study about Chloroquine prophylaxis for Covid-19	2	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Want to side effect of medicine, advantage and disadvantage?	2	safety and risk benefit	

CR2	Information about a chance to have side effect from medicine + management approach if there're side effect occur.	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
CR2	Side effect of Chloroquine	2	safety and risk benefit	
CR2	☒don't know if the risk of side effect by taking the drug is justified by the low risk of getting COVID here in Thailand. Maybe in Thailand among healthcare workers it might be 2 %. Is it worth it?	3	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
CR2	☒Would participate if there is more PCR screening in Chaing Rai people (maybe 10% of total population) because it makes knowledge about the disease more e.g. factors, transmission, and chance. And it will make this study has benefits.	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	☒Because, first nowadays Covid-19 infection has unclear proven factors. Second, Chloroquine has side effect to patients and complication. Third, There aren't too many people get Covid-19 infection in Chiang Rai, the effective of research is not enough.	1	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
CR2	☒Not confident in the effectiveness of the drug because current treatment has not seen the good effects of this medicine.	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Want to participate if there is paper support	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Want to join, I will know how to use anti-covid medicine	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Because it look at the treatment, how it benefits	1	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	What info? Explain the reasons, how CQ action in Covid prophylaxis? And how has it effective more than wearing appropriate PPE?	2	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
CR2	I want to know the mechanism of drug action more clearly.	2	social value and st. rationale	

CR2	Support information about Chloroquine prophylaxis effectiveness	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Mechanism of CQ action in COVID prophylaxis	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	First, has papers support Chloroquine can be really prevent Covid. Second, Medical professor who we respect is also participate this study. Third, it is the hospital policy that every personnel should participate	2	social value and st. rationale	other
CR2	Choose target population who are really contact Covid-19 because some population are not contact at all but they have to take medicine?	2	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
CR2	Report high incident rate, mortality rate in work place area	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	I want to see case study that has been experimented on all genders, all ages and experiment with patients with underlying diseases	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	Has mortality rate or serious illness of Covid in healthcare workers	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	I would like to know Chloroquine mechanism, how is it help on prophylaxis. Detail of side effect surveillance of research study.	2	social value and st. rationale	design and commitments
CR2	Has prelim study from using medicine for prophylaxis that works and don't have side effect	2	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
CR2	Clearly mechanism for prevent virus -> should not have	2	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	What is the mechanism through which CQ works against cell infection?	3	social value and st. rationale	

CR2	Based on my knowledge CQ has an anti-inflammatory action and this would decrease the damage to the lung during infection but would not help for prevention	3	social value and st. rationale	
CR2	I am concerned about the timeline of this study and competing alternative measures. It will take a few months to get this started, then anotherer few months duration and at that time (in 6-7 months or one year) then the vaccination might come out, which would be a better preventive measure	3	social value and st. rationale	social value and st. rationale
CR2	Do you have to take CQ for three months before it is effective in preventing disease and then keep on taking it? How is it exactly planned? I would like to know more details	3	social value and st. rationale	design and commitments
CR2	If I takes CQ for three months, how long will the prophylactic effect last after that? How long is there a risk for side effects?	3	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
FTM	But concern about the long duration of the study-high chances of loss follow-up	1	design and commitments	
FTM	If use a lot of time during follow up (like waiting for many hours), may not join (-difficult for work)	2	design and commitments	
FTM	If need frequent follow up, less attractive	2	design and commitments	
FTM	Procedures-venipuncture many times	2	design and commitments	
FTM	No travel compensation	2	design and commitments	
FTM	Drug-related AE- any treatment provide?	2	design and commitments	
FTM	What to do if get sick during the study?	2	design and commitments	
FTM	Better than nothering.	1	safety and risk benefit	
FTM	Concern about side effects, especially in long-term use	2	safety and risk benefit	

FTM	May have some additional effect in protecting the disease	1	social value and st. rationale	
HCM	Given the fact that chloroquine could cause a prolonged QT interval, should the participants be performed ECG before they start dosing to see if they have any risk factors for develop prolongation of QT intervals? During 30 days of taking drug at home, wi	3	design and commitments	
HCM	In case that I forget a drug dose on one day, what should I do? Do I need to take 2 doses on the next day OR take 1 dose only?	3	design and commitments	
HCM	In case that someone has to come back to their hometown and leaves study drug blister at home, how many missing doses could lead to discontinuation of study drug?	3	design and commitments	
HCM	History of hypertension and cardiovascular diseases	1	safety and risk benefit	
HCM	Congenital anomaly: only one kidney	1	safety and risk benefit	
HCM	Some paper showed that chloroquine is not effective for COVID-19 patients, this drug can even cause some side effects, especially on cardiovascular syste	1	safety and risk benefit	
HCM	We need preliminary data on safety and efficacy from otherer trials using chloroquine in COVID-19 therapeutics and prophylaxis	1	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale
HCM	Information about safety and efficacy of chloroquine	2	safety and risk benefit	social value and st. rationale

HCM	<p>We have to admit that we do not have many COVID-19 cases in Vietnam who were enrolled in the chloroquine trial (VICO), hence we could not say anything about the efficacy of this drug in our patients. However, we still need more information/data regarding safety and efficacy of chloroquine in both treatment and prophylaxis for COVID-19 so that we can consider whether or not we should participate in this trial. The side effect of chloroquine on QT intervals is the one that we concern most. If OUCRU could share with us some preliminary data or papers about efficacy and safety of chloroquine in COVID-19, we could then share this information on our private group so that everyone can have an idea about it. Of note, this information should be translated into Vietnamese so that everyone can easily read and understand.</p>	3	safety and risk benefit	
HCM	<p>In a clinical trial in Vietnam which uses chloroquine to manage COVID-19 patients (VICO trial), our observation in two patients at ward D showed that this drug could not reduce the viral load. In contrast, the more drug tablets they took, the higher viral load increased day after day. In particular, one of these two patients developed a prolongation of QT intervals, a serious side effect of chloroquine. Luckily, this patient did not meet the criteria of study drug discontinuation, but we had to monitor her closely by clinical assessment and serial ECG</p>	1	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
HCM	<p>Some papers showed that chloroquine is not effective in COVID-19 patients. This drug can even cause many side effects, especially on cardiovascular system. For those, who got COVID-19, because there is no available specific treatment for this disease, these patients agreed to take chloroquine with the hope that it can save their life (they actually have no choice). However, for us, the healthcare workers, we are using full PPE to take care of COVID-19 patients. In my opinion, it is hard to convince us to participate in this study if we have to take a drug that is not effective but can even cause many side effects.</p>	3	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
LAO	<p>Want to join but want to know more about the objective and methodology</p>	1	design and commitments	
LAO	<p>Yes, I want to join and want to know the dose and drug interaction</p>	1	design and commitments	

LAO	Will join and need to know more about the timeline	1	design and commitments	
LAO	I'm hesitant because I do not know the detail of inclusion criteria for this study	1	design and commitments	
LAO	Want to know more about the objective, methodology, outcome:	2	design and commitments	design and commitments
LAO	Do you think there are the bias if some think they had placebo and they take chloroquine by themselves?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Does this study conduct only with health care worker?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	How do you know if participant take drug or not?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Do you have insurance if the side effect occur to participant?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Where do you take the participant? Only from Mahosot hospital?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Do resident doctor can be participated? But they do not fix in Mahosot, they need to rotate to otherer hospital?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	In my ward, there is one doctor who got hypertension, DM and Cirrhosis, Can he join the study?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Why do you need to include the participant who has chronic disease?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	If the participant had taken chloroquine, can they participate to the study?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	When dose the study start?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	After taking chloroquine during 2 months, when will we know the result if chloroquine can prevent Covid-19?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	If I want to participant, how can we take the drug and where?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Can my family be recruited?	2	design and commitments	
LAO	Yes, want to join but want to know more detail about this study	1	other	

LAO	Because chloroquine use for antimalarial	1	other	
LAO	This is an excellent study	1	other	
LAO	We do not know when covid-19 will disappear	1	other	
LAO	The side effect of chloroquine is really small	1	safety and risk benefit	
LAO	Nothing to lose if I join the study because we do not have the medicine to prevent or to treat covid-19 yet	1	safety and risk benefit	
LAO	I don't know what is the side effect of the chloroquine	1	safety and risk benefit	
LAO	I'm allergic to many food, many medicine, and do you think I participant the study? (I have never taken chloroquine)	2	safety and risk benefit	
LAO	This study can provide the real information and good for the health system of our country	1	social value and st. rationale	social value and st. rationale
LAO	To improve the quality of the prevention and the treatment	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	To prove if chloroquine can be used or not for the prevention of covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Yes, I want to join because chloroquine is already included in the treatment of Covid-19 and it was one of the medicines to treat SARS	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Chloroquine is easy to find and not too expensive	1	social value and st. rationale	social value and st. rationale
LAO	Yes, want to know if it works, if it does not work, it helps to search for anotherer medicine	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Yes, because it is helpful for the doctors to be safe if this medicine is really efficacious	1	social value and st. rationale	

LAO	Yes, want to know the treatment of covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Yes, want to know the prevention of covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Yes, want to share this information to the population	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	To know more about chloroquine, if it really works to prevent from Covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Want to join because until now we do not have confirm treatment for covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	I personally agree to join, because it is the pilot study and it is very useful	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	It could help for the benefit of everyone	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Because covid-19 is dangerous	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	Totally agree to join because this can help the population to also get benefit from the study	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	No, because we do not have any confirmation if chloroquine can be used for the prevention	1	social value and st. rationale	
LAO	I can use otherer method to prevent myself from covid-19	1	social value and st. rationale	

MORU	CQ has a strong taste and known side effects, if placebo not matched, worried about blinding	1	design and commitments	
MORU	3 months duration sounds too long	1	design and commitments	
MORU	Time constraint (visiting student)	1	design and commitments	
MORU	The dose compared to dose in malaria prophylaxis?	3	design and commitments	
MORU	Living with time constraints	3	design and commitments	
MORU	What is the sample size?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Participants do develop COVID19 and do they have guarantee access to healthcare, hospitals?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Are there any otherer drugs which you think could work in prophylaxis study, its really urgent to get answers and waste all the effort at the same time, could you evaluate two drugs at the same time? Just in case you are not sure if this will work or not.	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Second question, are you going to use placebo that looks, taste like chloroquine?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Wondering what the outcome will be, will this be a clinical outcome or be screening a lot of asymptomatic with negative people, in possibly negative people?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	If there is a high chance it would work, would a crossover design help as all participants would get chloroquine eventually, or would it take too long?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Is it just chloroquine?	2	design and commitments	
MORU	Some people might feel that randomized controlled trial is in some way unfair, and if there are anyway you could provide insurance to the controls that the facility could give if the result is a positive. As well an prioritize benefits from the chloroquine.	3	design and commitments	
MORU	I like CQ	1	other	
MORU	I want to try sugar coated CQ	1	other	

MORU	I have never been in a MORU trial before – want the experience	1	other	
MORU	Need to be 1 participant in the sample size for study	1	other	
MORU	Are we in the right audience to ask these questions, because we will implement trials in hospitals may have overloads of cases taken part in the test, a priority chance if this works is 50-50?	3	other	
MORU	People in this room are very active on Facebook, and other social media. Should we spread all over social media or kept quiet.	3	other	
MORU	Probably yes, but I would like to know AE off CQ	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	CQ is a commonly used drug (good safety profile)	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Yes, minimal risk, maximum benefit	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Safe drug (no risk, just potential advantages)	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	increase chance to protect myself and others	1	safety and risk benefit	safety and risk benefit
MORU	side effects	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	afraid of side effects	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Don't know the potential risks	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	the treatment will not be cost-effective	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	need more information: what is the adverse effect of CQ?	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Need more information about drug	1	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Side-effect, need more information on the adverse effect of chloroquine	3	safety and risk benefit	
MORU	Contribute to have evidence to save people as well as my friends and family	1	safety and risk benefit	

MORU	It might work (probably better than nothing)	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I want to do it because I want the result to be known	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Finding new drugs is always important to overcome disease	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	It might work (probably better than nothing)	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I don't want to infect otherers	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	it could be an informative trial	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	If CQ works it might help otherer people	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	contribute to the development of a new treatment	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	To help knowledge if it might work or not	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Help mankind	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Contribute to have evidence to save people as well as my friends and family	1	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit

MORU	Would like to have contribution to this	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Yes I want to help find prevention	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	I want to know if CQ might be helpful for the situation now	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	For helping the humanity	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Prophylaxis drug is needed	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	for humanity	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	3 months prophylaxis for a disease with an average duration of 10 days, not rational	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	What if I became asymptomatic carrier and spread further?	1	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	How regularly are we testing people because if you give the healthcare worker the chloroquine, and they still get covid19 but they do get it very mildly or asymptotically would it make them not realize that they are potentially spreading it to otherer normal people? I just don't know if the chloroquine start becoming infected tiny or you got infected but very mildly that you don't know that you actually infected. So, if you are not testing people if they are shedding, would it be possible to tell if they are asymptomatic who are then potentially spreading it to otherer people because they don't know they are infected.	3	social value and st. rationale	design and commitments

MORU	If you have to given a long time and apply this to the population, for 3 months. It might be too dangerous for a lot of patients. That is my main concern.	3	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Healthcare workers are more pre-exposed?	3	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Working in a high-risk clinical area, would these people not be taking extra precautions like PPE? Will there be high enough risk of infection to determine the difference between the group?	3	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
MORU	In terms of number, I am assuming this is going to be held in Thailand, right now the numbers are pretty low and there is no certainty it will run up the same way like Europe. We could have too few cases to say that it is useful or not.	3	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Is it ethical to use a drug with a potential treatment effect in a large prophylaxis study, because you might increase the risk of a mutation developing to immune to the chloroquine?	2	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Chloroquine in treatment is not used to eliminate the virus but to treat the resulting symptom inflammatory. So, the rolling resistance presumably be relisted?	2	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	In terms of enrolling people into the study, are there many otherer alternative approaches?	2	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	If chloroquine is being use in patients with Rheumatoid arthritis which is an auto-immune disease, is there any evidence that the chloroquine providing these people with protection against COVID19, in terms of being infected, disparity of the infection?	2	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Why 3 months?	2	social value and st. rationale	
MORU	Loyal to MORU but: a priori chance it works is not very high	1	social value and st. rationale	

NPL	Has otherer disease for which taking many otherer medications so if added this it will be more medicines to consume	1	design and commitments	
NPL	Being eligible for the study	1	design and commitments	
NPL	No one thought about whom will bear health expense if participant get sick during research study?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	You said that our health insurance is covered only for three months. But what happens if, side effects of drugs are seen after three months?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	I am under treatment for Migraine. Can I participate in this study?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Do we need to withdraw 10 ml blood? Will subjects be ready to withdraw such large amount of blood?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	What are the inclusion and exclusion criteria?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Does this study conducted only with working health care worker?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	How many total sample need to be recruited?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Recently, I had similar symptoms of COVID-19, but during investigation I was tested negative. So can I participate in the study?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	How much is the sample size?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Do we get treatment if we become sick during study?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Did you say during enrollment we will get either Chloroquine or anotherer medicine?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	What is the frequency and duration of this drug?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	At what time do we need to take this medicine?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	What is the process of enrollment in the study?	3	design and commitments	

NPL	Do we have insurance coverage if we get sick during study?	3	design and commitments	
NPL	10 ml blood is much to withdraw	1	design and commitments	
NPL	Long duration (90 days) to take medicine daily for healthy subject	3	design and commitments	
NPL	Might not be possible to remember to take medicine daily while working in hospital which may lead to Non-compliance	1	design and commitments	
NPL	Fear of Side-effects on the body	1	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	Co-morbidities	1	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	Being healthy individual doesn't want to consume	1	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	Prevents from further complications of COVID-19 n=1	1	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	Recently I have done valve replacement, am diabetic and taking too many medicines. So don't these drugs will bring ill effect if I consume one more medicine?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	I am a healthy individual. Why should I take this drug?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	We have heard about cardio-toxicity as major side effects of this drug? So, is it safe to use?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	I am concerned about the drug interaction. So, which drugs are contraindicated while taking chloroquine?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	I have Hypertension and Diabetes. Can I take this medicine?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	We are concerned about the side effects of this drug. Can you explain about this?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	What are the risk and benefit of this drug?	3	safety and risk benefit	
NPL	Side-effects might occur as medicine has to take long duration i.e. 90 days.	1	safety and risk benefit	

NPL	Media influence that Chloroquine is not effective for COVID-19 prevention	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	There are no otherer options so far such as any vaccine.	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Ensure safety from COVID-19 infection after enrolling in this study	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Will keep subject under close observation of experts and help to get treated immediately when needed	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Target population is healthcare providers who are delivering health services for COVID-19.	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Prevents from COVID-19 infection	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Contribute to the study	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	How long do Chloroquine as a prophylaxis will prevent against COVID-19?	3	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Prevents from COVID-19 infection according to your study protocol	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	We are working in threat conditions and study drugs might help to prevent from COVID-19 infection	1	social value and st. rationale	
NPL	Source of motivation to general population to take drugs in future	1	social value and st. rationale	

OUH1	short duration, if able to stop half way due to side effects. Might not remember to take meds regularly (duration). Risk and benefits.	2	design and commitments	safety and risk benefit
OUH1	Knowing the outcomes being looked at in the study. Potential benefits vs potential side effects/complications. Intensity of monitoring. Potential risks to those with otherer health conditions.	2	design and commitments	safety and risk benefit
OUH1	none	2	other	
OUH1	More information	2	other	
OUH1	unsure of medication, interactions with current meds, side effects	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Knowledge of side effects, reassurance of medical health for myself, how invasive and how frequent are the tests	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
OUH1	need more info on side effects and risks of the drug	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	need more info on side effects of the drugs, if chance of severe side effects would not agree to participate	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Side effects, would you be able to have medications if positive or negative	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments
OUH1	what does strength and side effects	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	No because of side effects it may have. I'm on otherer medication at this time and would be worried if this would affect me	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	only if it guaranteed it would not affect my otherer meds	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Not interested, worried it might cause side effects on me	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	side effects, having children in case anything happens to me	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Information on potential risks/side effects How many visits/attendances required. Any exclusion criteria	2	safety and risk benefit	design and commitments

OUH1	Unsure - No because I would need more information but depending on side effects would depend if I would do it	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Side effects – short term and long term	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Possible toxicity? But I'm blinded so I won't know	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	What side effects the drug would give me. Any long term problems	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	No because risk of side effects/negative effects impacting ability to work/health (including risk from otherer illnesses due to immunocompromise)	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	help with covid treatment research	1	social value and st. rationale	

OUH1	Any form of medication that would help prevent covid-19 from spreading and being able to treat COVID-19	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Yes because at the moment there are not otherer options to prevent the virus contamination and this virus is a pandemic in the whole world	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Yes because help to develop prophylaxis regime plus likely to improve general health as increased clinic visits/medical input	1	social value and st. rationale	safety and risk benefit
OUH1	Yes because worth trialling to see if there actually a benefit	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Yes because finding something to combat/prevent Covid-19 would be amazing and save lives	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	If a similar trial had taken place and had good results I would consider taking it	2	social value and st. rationale	

OUH1	Yes because potential to offer significant benefit to those infected with COVID	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Knowledge of the drug and side effects – short or long term	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	How many attendances/visits required?	2	design and commitments	
OUH1	If participating in the study would affect the quality of the care received if diagnosed with COVID	2	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Reassurance of medical health for myself	2	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	How invasive are the tests?	2	design and commitments	
OUH1	If duration shorter	2	design and commitments	
OUH1	If it was aimed at treatment rather than prophylaxis	2	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	If guaranteed would not affect other medications already on	2	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Exclusion criteria	2	design and commitments	
OUH1	Knowing the outcomes being looked at in the study	2	design and commitments	
OUH1	contribute on body of reasearch on COVID	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	easy to comply with one dose	1	design and commitments	
OUH1	may reduce the severity of COVID in me	1	social value and st. rationale	
OUH1	Improve my general health as increased clinic visits/medical input	1	social value and st. rationale	

OUH1	Side effects (drug quite toxic)	1	design and commitments	safety and risk benefit
OUH1	duration too long	1	design and commitments	
OUH1	on other medication and worried about effects	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	needle phobia	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Doesn't like to take any medication unless absolutely necessary	1	safety and risk benefit	
OUH1	Breastfeeding and worried about that	1	safety and risk benefit	

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question

Theme 3

safety and risk benefit
social value and st. rationale

